

Precision Polarized Bandwidth Expansion

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Abstract

The Armed Forces has a long standing requirement for a robust global communications infrastructure to support real time operations. The bandwidth elasticity continues to be tested as demand continues to grow in support of multiple theater events. The US Army CERDEC Space and Terrestrial Communications Directorate, coupled with the US Navy is doing relevant research and development in order to expand the boundaries within the physics that govern bandwidth usage today. Such bandwidth economizing will aid systems being developed in support of both MILSATCOM and commercial frequency bands at the data rates required to support the battlefield. High speed digitization coupled with carrier code identifiers will be used to achieve usage beyond the conventional means of operation. In the development of polarizing with precision, multiple sampling techniques at various frequency domains will be evaluated for best suited applications. The US Army CERDEC SATCOM laboratories located at Aberdeen Proving Ground, MD is working with the US Navy and industry to evaluate and determine the most effective approach in expanding polarization techniques. The focus of testing will primarily consist of data recovery with signals of interest operating on the same frequency in three or more different polarizations simultaneously. Results from such testing will be used to effect polarizing with precision and determine the predictability using discriminate line of site and long haul applications. Functional variables will include angle of arrival, geographical origin of emission versus destination of delivery. Discussions will be principally focused on accomplishing data recovery using multi variant polarization techniques.

Background

The media within long haul communications has been technically restricted in the reuse of a single frequency due to our handling of energy for a carrier operating at any given frequency. One very innovative way is to use a method known as Carrier in Carrier (CnC). CnC is a method in which requires full duplex operations, point to point, with the same modem at each end. This feature was mastered by COMETECH EF DATA. The demodulator receives the local modulator transmission along with its distant end's transmission simultaneously. The demodulator deploys an adaptive cancelation technique to discard its transmission, and then processes the desired receive signal. The cost to this technique is the expenditure of slightly more power than the carriers would expend on independent frequencies but the bandwidth occupancy is reduced to the largest carrier's bandwidth. This technique is a significant advancement in reuse and occupy's far less bandwidth compared to using two independent frequencies. As with all reuse, energy also plays a role in this pairing scheme in that the higher order of modulation, the more energy sensitive the demodulation is. In maintaining good in-phase and quadrature signal constellations, energy has to have a degree of prevalence. Below are two charts of data that reflect the performance associated with an order of modulation. Additional measurements are reflected by the testing of various coding enhancements. The increase in energy levels at the demodulator of the undesired transmission versus the desired reception is referred in the chart as CnC ratio. As you can see the first chart reflects QPSK degradation in respect to CnC ratio.

As the CnC ratio increases, the performance degrades but with QPSK, the levels have to be significant to see an impact.

In this chart you can see the same constraints applied to a higher order of modulation, 8PSK.

The take away here is that as the ratio of energy level increases in the undesired signal, the degradation begins to reflect. The CnC feature is significant technical advancement and somewhat underutilized at this time.

Another form of frequency reuse is achieved by separating the energy at a given frequency by orienting the signal differently. This separation of energy can be done in three principle techniques referred to as circular, elliptical and linear. These techniques of separating energy are employed during the long haul phase of the communications and typically independent of each technique.

The circular polarization directs the signal circularly as its name implies by slowing the vertical portion of the signal by 1/4 wavelength (90°) giving it the appearance of being circular. Below is a representation of a circularly polarized signal where the vertical and horizontal planes in respect to the 'z' axis (frequency) are pierced repeatedly.

The opposite direction minimizes interference. In a similar fashion, elliptical polarization rotates throughout the planes but is varied in a skew as shown here;

The linear polarization differentiates energy by orienting the signal to a plane and affixing it in relation to adjacent planes. This method shown below reflects a simple means of orientation, remaining in the planes of the operational origin. It is deployed perpendicularly for separation purposes.

Many of the commercial satellite constellations as well as some military satellites constellations maximize the advantage of using some form of polarizing concept. The ground segment polarization must match the concept employed in long haul space applications therefore deploying a variety of polarizations on a long haul line of sight application is far easier.

Of these concepts of single frequency reuse, not excluding the long time favorites such as Code Division Multiple Access (CDMA), and Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA), and now with the advent of CnC, at least for the moment, appears to have maximized reuse at post-long haul receive processing. The remaining areas for exploitation are in the long haul domain of itself. Long haul media is the most expensive in terms of tax dollars to the Government in either procurement or commercial leasing so any savings will potentially impact significantly. Out of the long haul reuse schemes, the linear polarization technique has the maximum opportunity for energy occupancy exploitation. With that, our exploration focuses on linear polarization expansion because it offers low cost commercial components to experiment with and minimizes risk in comparison.

Work At Hand

We are focusing the effort to take shape by assembling an experimental system comprised of commercially available high speed Analog to Digital Converters (ADC) integrated directly with waveguide assemblies capable of passing a singular and dual linearly polarized signal.

Conventional means of determining energy concentrations will be utilized with independent channelized high speed instrumented tests. Typical power meter/spectrum analyzer pairs are used for dual port quadrant reference monitoring while a preamp spectrum analyzer is used on the targeted single port.

Initial Test Characterization & Validation

The exploration of reaching such a significant goal requires multiple experiments to ensure we are testing with absolute precision polarization. Because we are typically operating with high orders of modulation, testing will evolve into the PSK waveform sampling and modeling. Initially however, we will begin with the simplest form of energy measurements using an unmodulated signal. In keeping with predictability, we will use a simple mathematical description of a sine wave where as a function of time (t) is;

$$y = \alpha \sin (\omega t + \phi)$$

The formula variables are α as the amplitude, ω is the angular frequency (number of cycles, in radians) and ϕ reflects phase and (t) is '0' within the sine wave. We are using the mathematical description in approximating a waveform, expressed as;

$$y = C + \alpha \sin (\omega t + \phi) + E$$

The formula variables added are C as a constant representing the mean value and E is the error in sequencing. As we test, we are formulating an expected response and measuring with an accurate constant level, the error off axis, or lack of energy in a given plane. Discussions in taking measurements to determining values can encompass a myriad of ways. These ways can begin varying the source versus varying the receiver. Additional receivers may be employed for accuracy as well as adding phased arrays with group control. A specific period of time will be set aside for the phased array topic. We are verifying a cause and effect predictability by setting up a receive waveguide on a fixed precision variable positioner in a sealed environment along with a fixed constant source.

The waveguide¹ will be aligned to a maximum receive signal strength (*maxrss*) of the polarization, represented as the zero delta position ($0\Delta = \text{maxrss}$). In parallel we will use receive waveguide² (*x,y*), waveguide³ (*x,-y*), waveguide⁴ (*-x,-y*), and waveguide⁵ (*-x,y*), fixed to serve as a references for source stability monitoring and receive error verification. By varying waveguide¹'s position by $1/n$ (where *n* denotes the level of precision) degree step size in the same direction, we can set the range of polarization susceptibility by accumulating to where the minimum receive signal strength is measured (*minrss*). Notating that *r* is the Δ (in radians) between *maxrss* + *minrss*, and since *maxrss* is defined at 0, we can express the range of data gathering as $(0\Delta + (1/n) r)$.

Determining Angles of Operation

To ensure the beam width and polarity variants are captured, a standard deviation (mean value) can be established over time within each measurement point of $1/n r$ with strength of $\alpha\theta$ in respect to 0Δ . Once the minimal strength $\alpha\theta$ is determined, the $(0\Delta - (1/n) r)$ will also be exercised in test to validate the complex conjugate of the signal to establish a full range of energy model in respect to 0Δ . With both $(0\Delta - (1/n) r)$ and $(0\Delta + (1/n) r)$, the value of the error at angle of polarization (*eap*) of θ and $-\theta$ introduced adjacently the full range is expressed as $2 \bullet \theta eap$, which identifies minimum amplitude *ma* required for successful signal processing at θ polarization. In approximating values, we can now adjust the sinusoidal model using the *ma* as a constant and error using $2\theta\phi$ as an addition to biasing to begin targeting a sampling model as;

$y = ma + \alpha \bullet \sin(2\pi\omega t + \phi) + \text{biasing} + 2\theta eap$. By maintaining independent monitors for waveguide², waveguide³, waveguide⁴, and waveguide⁵, for a cross-referencing delta, we will establish character of both the source and waveguide¹ under test. As we begin to deviate from 0Δ , preserving the relational value of *y* as it relates between the cross reference waveguides. In calculating the angles of operation, the deviation, or angle of error, in relation to any given targeted angle of polarization, the full range of energy manipulation for coherent demodulation is modeled. We are calculating the model with the assumption that the origin of signal travel (*z* axis) remains oriented the same throughout its transmission. The angles of interest are expressed as;

$$A1 = a1 \cos(\theta1 - \phi1) + a2 \cos(\theta2 - \phi1) + \dots + an \cos(\theta n - \phi1)$$

$$\text{Ending repetitions with; } An = a1 \cos(\theta1 - \phi n) + a2 \cos(\theta2 - \phi n) + \dots + an \cos(\theta n - \phi n).$$

¹ First waveguide, single orientation (0,0)

² Second waveguide, dual orientation (x,y)

³ Third waveguide, dual orientation (-x,y)

⁴ Fourth waveguide, dual orientation (-x,-y)

⁵ Fifth waveguide, dual orientation (x,-y)

The angular values are depicted graphically using 2 dimensions in relation to the horizontal axis as follows;

Determining Boundaries of Minimum Interference

Establishing boundaries of opportunity is a topic for discussion. Should the boundaries be defined based on angular operation? The horizontal plane could contain a disproportionate amount of energy to the vertical plane. Should energy volume be quantified in terms of angle or by dividing the energy into a maximum value per quadrant between vertical and horizontal? We are assuming for simplicity sake each angle has a proportionate amount of energy within a normal distribution. The deviation of energy from the targeted angle of signal of interest segmented by peak angle to peak off angle, and accounting for the respective the complex conjugate, we are defining a segment angular energy consumption represented below.

$C(x + y) = x - y$ as is the $C(y - x) = -x - y$ with no specific filtering at the vertex of the center frequency (0,0) and assuming the perpendicular polarization is similarly occupied, the principle targeted space for energy occupation remains within angle d .

Alternate presentation using the 3rd dimension

Arbitrary Angles of Opportunity

Polarization	Jones Vector	Typical <u>ket</u> Notation [†]
Linear polarized in the x-direction- Typically called 'Horizontal'	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$ H\rangle$
Linear polarized in the y-direction- Typically called 'Vertical'	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$	$ V\rangle$
Linear polarized at 45° from the x-axis- Typically called 'Diagonal' L+45	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$	$ D\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(H\rangle + V\rangle)$
Linear polarized at -45° from the x-axis- Typically called 'Anti-Diagonal' L-45	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}$	$ A\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(H\rangle - V\rangle)$
Right Hand Circular Polarized- Typically called RCP or RHCP	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -i \end{pmatrix}$	$ R\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(H\rangle - i V\rangle)$
Left Hand Circular Polarized- Typically called LCP or LHCP	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ i \end{pmatrix}$	$ L\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(H\rangle + i V\rangle)$

The R.C. Jones table above reflects the corresponding vectoring to the subject angles of exploration. Jones specifically termed the subject possibility of signal occupancy as the diagonal and anti-diagonal areas of polarization.

Handling The Challenges

Clearly any sort of adaptive cancelation would be ideal but even then, the sensitivity between signals and orders of modulation propose issues of an energy imbalance. In waveguide construction, the 'a' side of the waveguide (wide side) is directly proportional to the frequency. The 'b' side is normal to energy. The 'b' side is not always $a/2$. Can we slightly alter the 'b' side of the waveguide that results in requiring more power but provides more isolation? Below is a crude representation of the end of a 4 angle feed assembly of what modifying the 'b' side might look like;

The desired axial ratio between either pair of perpendicular interfaces is to be no more than 0.5dB. Additionally, are there any efficiencies that can be made in the materials used to aid in the discarding of the adjacent energy? We are looking forward to discussions on isolation concepts. All avenues towards reduction of interference are welcomed. This of course includes coherent adaptive cancelation as well as changing elements of the waveguide, using different materials for construction and varying sizes. With the concept of all transmissions sharing a common origin and frequency, regardless of polarization, shall traverse with equal relationship across equal media. If this assertion is correct, then can a feedback loop be provided to a store and forward scheme?

Summary

CERDEC is committed in economizing the use of a single frequency and to improve the Army's and Navy's throughput at our current frequency bands of operation. The potential tax dollar savings for bandwidth to the Army alone makes this goal worthwhile.

Our efforts in using supercooled demodulation have provided more control and closer to the interfacing directly to the waveguide than ever before. The use of Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) assets for post In-phase and Quadrature (I&Q) digital streams to recover data has proven high speed digitizing at the media frequency viable. The minimum acceptable outcome will be successful if Government has a complete understanding and capability of single waveform exploitation, advanced modifiable signal development, advanced developmental and acquisition strategies and most of all a closer relationship between industry and services.

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